

EFFECT OF “FUZZY” FIBER MORPHOLOGY ON THE INTERNAL GEOMETRY OF TEXTILE COMPOSITES CHARACTERIZED BY MICRO-COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

CNT growth can change the processibility of fibers and textiles on which they were grown and affect the meso and microstructure of the composite. This can have an impact on properties of the composite such as progressive damage development. In the present work, we study the effects of grafted CNTs on the internal geometry of a textile composite. Radially aligned CNTs were grown on microfibers within the alumina fabric using chemical vapor deposition. Afterwards, the CNT-modified fabrics were used to manufacture laminates by vacuum assisted resin infusion. Four types of composites were produced that differed in the CNT length and composite production conditions. The internal geometry of the produced laminates was characterized using micro-computed tomography. CNTs were found to increase the “effective” microfiber diameter; this effect was proportional to the CNT length. Short CNTs (~4-6 μm) did not significantly affect the laminate thickness and the yarn geometry whereas long CNTs (~17-19 μm) led to a doubling of the laminate thickness compared to the reference material without CNTs. In order to achieve the same fiber volume fraction as in the reference composite, the composite with long CNTs was also produced with additional pressure that achieved the desired fiber volume fraction as well as altered internal structure of the textile.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composites (FRCs) possess excellent in-plane mechanical properties, but their out-of-plane properties are relatively limited. One of the strategies to improve the through-thickness performance of the traditional FRCs is to incorporate nanofibers, such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs), either in the interlaminar or intralaminar region [1-4].

Growing CNTs on fibers (producing so-called “fuzzy” fibers) has a number of advantages for FRCs over other approaches as it avoids challenges related to CNT dispersion and provides an opportunity to achieve higher CNT loadings. This method also offers a high level of control over density, distribution, length, and alignment of the CNTs [5, 6]. Nanotubes can be grown perpendicular to the fiber surface as aligned arrays, which may have additional benefits for the composite performance [1]. Recent advances in the CNT grafting method allowed improving interlaminar

properties of “fuzzy” fiber reinforced plastic (FFRP) without decreasing the composite’s intralaminar properties [7, 8].

The improved properties of the hierarchical FRCs based on CNT-grafted fibers have attracted increasing attention to the manufacturability of such composites. In order to accurately estimate manufacturing parameters and produce FFRP with controlled properties, advanced knowledge about the influence of the CNT growth on different aspects of CNT-grafted fiber reinforcements is required.

The available literature suggests that CNT growth changes the processibility of fibers and textiles on which they are grown [9, 10]. For example, an increase in compression resistance was observed by Lomov et al. [11], particularly for aligned CNTs. This change in compressibility means that parameters of composite manufacturing may need readjustment to achieve the same fiber volume fraction as in the composite without CNTs.

One can also expect that the internal geometry of the CNT-grafted fabrics and, consequently, physical and mechanical properties of such hybrid composites may be different from those of a composite without CNTs. Indeed, the same study reported an increase in the fabric/yarn thickness. Similar to the compressibility studies, aligned CNTs showed a higher increase in thickness compared to random CNTs for the same nanofiber volume fraction and the same applied pressure [11].

Thus, it is expected that changes in the compression resistance of the fiber preform and the laminate thickness inflicted by the CNT growth are accompanied by the geometrical rearrangement of microscopic fibers. This is focus of the present work. We examine the effect of grafted CNTs of different lengths on the internal geometry of textile composites.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The alumina fabric used in this study (Cotronics Ultra-Temp 391) is a woven textile with a plain-weave, an areal density of 371 g/m², a yarn linear density of 221 tex, and an ends/picks count of 11.9/4.9 yarns/cm. The resin used for manufacturing the composite laminates is an aerospace grade resin which is based on a tetrafunctional epoxy resin (tetraglycidylether of 4,4'-diaminophenyl methane (TGDDM)).

2.1.1 Aligned carbon nanotube growth process

In order to deposit the catalyst precursor (Fe) on the textile substrate, the alumina textile was soaked in a 50 mM solution of iron nitrate (Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, Alfa Aesar) in isopropanol and then was dried over night at a temperature of ~30°C. This allows the catalyst particles to cover all fiber surfaces so that CNTs are grown all over the substrate even within the tows.

Fabric swatches of 4.5 cm × 15 cm were then cut from the catalyst deposited cloth tape and were placed in the middle of a tube furnace (Lindberg Blue M) with a tube diameter of ~5 cm (2”). The catalyst coating was then reduced to Fe particles under the flow of hydrogen at a furnace setpoint of 650°C [6, 12]. At the next step, ethylene was introduced to the substrate at the same temperature (650 °C) to start the CNT growth. Radially aligned CNTs were grown on the surface of the fibers in two different lengths by changing the duration of the ethylene exposure. Longer CNTs were obtained with ~3 min of ethylene exposure [13]. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of the CNT-grafted fabric carried out later on, confirmed a nanofiber length of ~17-19 μm in this case. These aligned CNT “forests” are expected to exhibit a “Mohawk” morphology [6]. Shorter CNTs with a length of ~4-6 μm were grown with ~1 min of ethylene exposure [13], where a radially aligned morphology is expected [6].

2.1.2 Composite manufacturing

Composite laminates were produced by vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) method [13]. In each case, 6 plies were stacked in a VARI setup consisted of distribution and flow medium, and porous Teflon peel plies. Fabric plies in the VARI setup were sandwiched between steel and glass plates and then the whole assembly was enclosed by a vacuum bag. Rigid spacers with a fixed

thickness were employed to maintain the uniformity of the laminates during the manufacturing process.

In the case of fabrics with long radially aligned CNTs, an additional laminate was produced to target the thickness and, hence, the alumina fiber volume fraction close to that of the reference (without CNTs) laminate. This was achieved by fixing the VARI setup between clamps, where the clamping pressure confined the thickness of the laminate to that of the spacers.

The laminate stack was then “demoisturized” under vacuum at 150°C for 2 hours, before the onset of resin infusion. Following removal of the residual moisture, the epoxy resin, previously degassed under vacuum at 80°C, is drawn into the laminate stack at 90°C at a vacuum pressure of 740 mmHg provided by a vacuum pump. The laminate is then cured at 160°C for 4 hours and post cured at 180°C for another 4 hours. In total, 4 types of laminates were produced:

- 1 – based on short aligned CNT-grafted fabric (the label “*Short*” will be used for this composite further in the text),
- 2 – based on long aligned CNT-grafted fabric (the label “*Long*” will be employed),
- 3 – based on long aligned CNT-grafted fabric with clamping pressure (hereafter referred to as “*LongP*”), and
- 4 – based on unmodified fabric (“*Reference*” material, without CNTs).

2.2 Characterization methods

2.2.1 SEM

Average length and morphology of the CNT forests grown on the surface of the fabrics were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using a Philips XL30 FEG SEM. Prior to microscopy, samples were coated with a thin layer of (Au/Pd).

2.2.2 Micro-CT

X-ray computed tomography (micro-CT) is a powerful non-destructive technique to visualize and quantitatively characterize material microstructure [14-16]. In this work micro-CT was employed to characterize internal geometry of the produced laminates. Samples of 10×10 mm² and 3×10 mm² were cut from the composite plates of each type using a diamond saw. The third dimension of the samples was preserved equal to the thickness of the laminates. A margin of 5 mm was kept from the edges of the plates. Afterwards, the prepared samples were scanned with Phoenix Nanotom X-ray tomography system. The samples of 10×10 mm² were glued together with a layer of adhesive tape and scanned as a stack. The 3×10 mm² samples were scanned separately. The tomographic acquisition was made with tube voltage of 100 kV and current of 216 μA for the stack of the samples and of 124-135 μA for the single samples. Voxel size was about 2 μm for the 3×10 mm² samples, and 6.3 μm for the 10×10 mm² samples. Afterwards, the acquired radiographs were converted into samples cross-sectional images.

2.2.2 Image analysis

In order to quantitatively characterize textile’s internal geometry, the cross-sectional images were further analyzed using ImageJ software (ver. 1.47) [17, 18] and in-house developed tools for image analysis. Thickness of the laminates was measured using two approaches. Firstly, five measurements were performed on each side of the samples using a digital caliper. The average value was accepted as the plate thickness value. Secondly, the thickness was estimated from the micro-CT images. For every sample twenty cross-sectional images uniformly distributed through the sample length and width were binarized. The space outside the sample was assigned the black color; the area inside of the sample (epoxy and the fabrics) was given the white color. Next, the binarized images were processed using an in-home developed code implemented in MATLAB. The code searched for the mean line of the sample’s cross-section and performed measurements with the step of one pixel perpendicularly to the mean line. The average value of these measurements was accepted as the thickness value.

ImageJ allows measuring length of lines and polylines, area, perimeter and a set of shape descriptors of arbitrary polygons outlined in the image. The results of measurements are represented in physical units providing that the scale is specified, which sets the physical size of a pixel in the image.

Thus, parameters like crimp and geometrical characteristics of the yarns, e.g. perimeter and aspect ratio, can be estimated.

Once the yarn contours are manually outlined in the cross-sectional images (Fig. 1 *left*), ImageJ can evaluate the shape parameters. Perimeter is the length of the yarns contour. Aspect ratio is defined as a ratio between major and minor axes of an ellipse which fits to an outlined polygonal shape of the yarn [18].

Crimp is a measure of the yarn waviness. In textiles it is defined as the ratio of the yarn's length to the fabric's length. The mean line of the yarns was outlined in the cross-sectional images which were chosen to be in the middle of the yarns (Fig. 1 *right*). The length of the fabric was estimated as a distance between the centers of two neighboring yarns. Thus crimp was calculated in both, warp and weft directions.

Figure 1: Yarns cross-sections (*left*) and yarns mean lines (*right*) outlined in the image using ImageJ.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SEM investigation of the “fuzzy” fiber-reinforced composites confirmed that in the case of short CNTs they were grown annularly around the fibers as shown in Fig. 2 *left*. Their length was estimated between 4 and 6 µm. Long CNTs with the length of ~17-19 µm exhibited the radially aligned “Mohawk” morphology (Fig. 2 *right*).

Fig. 3 shows a cross-sectional image of the stack of the laminates. One can notice that the microstructure of the laminates manufactured from the fabrics with CNTs looks altered in comparison with the reference laminate. Yarns appear to swell in CNT-modified composites. Nanotubes push fibers away from each other resulting in a lower local fiber volume fraction inside the yarns (Fig. 4).

Figure 2: SEM images of fibers with grown aligned CNTs: short CNTs of ~4-6 µm long (*left*) and long CNTs of ~17-19 µm (*right*). The scale bar is 20 µm in both images.

Figure 3: Micro-CT cross-sectional image of the laminates: *Reference* is the material without CNTs. *Short* is the composite with short CNTs. *Long* is the laminate produced from a fabric with long CNTs. *LongP* is the laminate with long CNTs produced under the additional pressure.

Figure 4: Micro-CT images of yarns' cross-section in the reference material (without CNTs) and in the composite with long CNTs.

Due to the yarn swelling the most obvious affected structural characteristic is the laminate thickness. Its measurements are summarized in Table 1. Indeed, it was found that all CNT-modified composites were thicker than the laminate without CNTs. Both measuring techniques confirmed this. Moreover, laminates with long CNTs (*Long*) had a much higher thickness (by a factor of two) compared to the *Reference* material.

Composite	Thickness measured with a caliper [mm]	Thickness assessed from the micro-CT images [mm]
<i>Reference</i>	1.68±0.006	1.58±0.010
<i>Short</i>	1.90±0.011	1.76±0.009
<i>Long</i>	3.55±0.012	3.46±0.016
<i>LongP</i>	1.80±0.009	1.64±0.012

Table 1: Average thickness of the laminate plates and its standard error.

The measurements performed physically using a digital caliper and by means of the micro-CT image analysis showed a good agreement. The average thickness values estimated from the analysis of the cross-sectional images was always lower compared to the values measured with the caliper. This result can be explained by errors introduced due to the laminate surface roughness and the caliper's rated accuracy of 0.02 mm.

The measured perimeter and area of yarn cross-sections are reported in Table 2. Yarns in the composites with long CNTs had a largest perimeter. That again confirmed the hypothesis of the yarns swelling after the CNT growth. Fibers inside the yarns of *Long* laminate were pushed away from each other by the grown CNTs and were forced to occupy available space in the thickness direction and in the fabric plane. Thus, due to the fiber rearrangement the yarns became more circular compared to the *Reference* material (Fig. 3). This is confirmed by the reduced aspect ratio. On the other hand, yarns in *LongP* laminate that were produced under pressure could not freely swell in the thickness direction due to the applied pressure. Therefore, their through-the-thickness expansion was limited. Instead fibers in the yarns had to migrate within the laminate plane leading to more elliptical cross-sections (Table 2). The aspect ratio of such yarns is the highest among the studied materials. No significant difference in the aspect ratio and perimeter was observed for *Short* laminate if compared to the *Reference* composite indicating that short CNTs did not have significant influence on the geometry of the yarn cross-section.

Composite	Perimeter [mm]	Aspect Ratio
<i>Reference</i>	2.02±0.017	4.7±0.14
<i>Short</i>	2.03±0.020	4.6±0.12
<i>Long</i>	2.52±0.032	2.7±0.13
<i>LongP</i>	2.50±0.042	6.5±0.26

Table 2: Average value of yarns perimeter and area in the laminate plates and their standard error.

Measurements of crimp showed that *Long* laminate had the highest crimp in the weft direction among all studied composites (Table 3). The yarns in this composite had freedom to expand due to CNT growth. The yarns swelled leading to the increased crimp owing to interlacing in the fabric. For *LongP* crimp was the lowest. Moreover, crimp of the *LongP* laminate in warp and weft directions was found to be the same, which can be attributed to the flattening of the yarns through the thickness direction under the applied pressure. *Short* laminate showed the decreased crimp in comparison with the *Reference* material. Possible explanations may be that the outer parts of the forest could be compressed, making the yarn path flatter, or perhaps because the CNT growth was not uniform along fibers in the yarns. The observation of un-grafted sections on a fiber extracted from a woven fabric was also made earlier in the literature, for example, Lachman et al. reported about a periodic CNT growth along the fibers [19]. Thus, in *Short* composite at the places of the yarn contacts, CNT loading and CNT length may be lower than the same parameters assessed along the fiber where there were no yarn interlacing. That might also result in flatter yarn paths.

Composite	Crimp in warp direction	Crimp in weft direction
<i>Reference</i>	0.019±0.002	0.031±0.001
<i>Short</i>	0.013±0.001	0.027±0.002
<i>Long</i>	0.020±0.003	0.053±0.006
<i>LongP</i>	0.019±0.004	0.019±0.003

Table 3: Crimp of the fabrics in the laminate plates and their standard error.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work influence of grafted CNTs of different length on the internal geometry of the textile composites was studied. For this purpose, radially aligned CNTs of different length were grown on the surface of an alumina fabric reinforcement using chemical vapor deposition. The “fuzzy” fabric was, afterwards, impregnated with an epoxy resin via VARI for manufacturing four types of the laminates: *Reference* (without CNTs), *Short* (with CNTs of ~4-6 μm), *Long* (with CNTs of ~17-19 μm) and *LongP* (with CNTs of ~17-19 μm under additional pressure in order to preserve the alumina fiber volume fraction as in the *Reference* composite).

It was found that yarns in the CNT-modified composites swelled due to the CNT grafting leading to the increase of the yarn dimensions and, consequently, to the laminate thickness. This effect was more pronounced in the composite with long CNTs. *Long* laminate had ~2X thickness compared to the *Reference* CNT-free material.

While the desired fiber volume fraction was successfully achieved in *LongP* composite, the laminate’s internal structure was significantly altered. Under the clamping pressure, the yarns were constrained in the thickness direction, such that the fibers migrated within the fabrics plane. Thus, the swelled yarns flattened out and their aspect ratio increased by a factor of 1.4 relative to the *Reference* material. In addition, the flattening of the yarns resulted in the lowest crimp in *LongP* composite, which was found to be the same in warp and weft directions. For other composites, crimp in the warp direction was lower than in the weft direction as it was expected.

The laminate with short CNTs showed decreased crimp in comparison with the *Reference* material. Possible explanations may be that the outer parts of the CNT forest could be compressed making the yarn path flatter, or, perhaps, because the CNT growth was not uniform along the microfiber length in the yarns.

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